

The Casanova Drift Model: An arable crop boom spray drift model

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Summary

Drift risk assessments (RA) in most countries rely on either Tier 1 drift tables (e.g. the EU) or simple statistical models derived from data (e.g. AgDisp in the USA, Australia, Brazil, etc.) resulting in buffer distances that can be excessively large and unrealistic. A major missing component of a tiered drift RA is an absence of publicly available and regulatory acceptable higher tier mathematical models that can provide conservative yet realistic estimates of spray drift – and here we expressly mean ground-based applications.

Thus, a refined mechanistic arable crop spray drift model – the Casanova Drift Model (CDM) – is presented. The model is a mixture of ballistic tracking of droplets (Lagrangian transport of water droplets through air in time) combined with equations dealing with droplet evaporation, a representation of the horizontal wind profile, an approximation of canopy effects, a droplet size distribution, and a simplified description of spray sheet breakup. A cloud-based computationally-efficient interface has been developed using the R-Shiny platform – a single run takes less than a minute – and the entire coding is in C++ and R.

The model has been calibrated and validated against not only Bayer (internal) field data but also European research data from four countries. Preliminary work assessing relative performance (i.e. relative changes in drift due to operational variables such as wind speed) and absolute performance (i.e. modelled drift curves that match results on the ground) are presented. The model includes modules that may help address issues raised during the SETAC DRAW discussions (e.g. sampler capture efficiency; locale). Plans are being made to have this model reviewed by key drift model experts. Afterwards, the source code, interface, and a library of droplet spectra for the standard flat fan nozzles used in EU drift trials will be made freely available.

Key words: Spray drift, modelling, mechanistic model

Introduction

Drift risk assessments (RA) in most countries rely on either Tier 1 drift tables (e.g. the EU Rautmann [1999] drift tables) or simple statistical models derived from data (e.g. AgDisp in the USA, Australia, Brazil, etc.) resulting in buffer distances that can be excessively large and unrealistic. In no regulatory domain is there a full tiered approach to drift RA, short of full-scale drift trials, and thus spray drift buffers are, rightly, conservative. This situation is far from ideal. What is needed is a tiered drift RA running from a very simple Tier 1 through refinements obtained from data bases (e.g. the SETAC Drift Risk Assessment Workshops [DRAW]: Mackay *et al.*, 2018) to statistical models based on that data, to mechanistic models that can extrapolate beyond limited data sets, to

full scale drift trials and their biological equivalents. Consequently, industry and regulators are in need of higher tier mathematical models that can provide conservative yet realistic estimates of spray drift – and here we expressly mean ground-based applications.

Two European drift models for arable crops already exist: SiMod (Silsoe Spray Application Unit, Silsoe, UK: Butler Ellis & Miller, 2010) and IDEFICS (Plant Research International, Wageningen, NL: Holterman *et al.*, 1997). However, neither model is strictly in the public domain and the code of neither model is available for further development work outside the hosting research institutes. Therefore, a refined mechanistic arable crop spray drift model has been developed – the Casanova Drift Model (CDM) – and is outlined below, with the explicit intent of putting this model, in its entirety, into the public domain.

Modelling spray drift with any accuracy is difficult because of the many components that need to be included in the calculation algorithm. For example, field dimensions, wind velocity profile with elevation over a crop, foliage density of different crops, droplet size distribution for the specific nozzle at a given pressure, evaporation of water from the droplets during transport, and of course, the driving force, atmospheric instability and how this affects turbulence and variation in wind direction – just to name a few. The need for a publicly available spray drift model that can provide enough accuracy while still being conservative in its prediction continues to be of great interest to the community.

The CDM has been developed specifically for this purpose, from the ground up, as a boom-based drift model. It is a mechanistic Lagrangian particle tracking model, with some semi-empirical correlations. As such, it is “ballistic” in nature, not relying on the drift table methods currently used to assess buffer lengths.

Model Description

Modelling of droplet movement from the time it leaves the nozzle till it lands on the ground is a multi-media problem. It includes breaking from the spray sheet, transport and continual evaporation in air, interaction with wind and crop canopy, and subsequent deposition. These processes are simulated in the CDM (Fig. 1) and described in sections below.

Fig. 1. CDM input, output, and simulated processes.

Drop size distribution

Droplet size distribution is a key input to the CDM and typically includes measurement of the cumulative volume of the spray for each droplet size. CDM requires this as an input for the tank mix, nozzle, and pressure combination for which spray drift needs to be simulated. Users are provided with three options to incorporate drop size distribution into the model: (1) extrapolation, (2) normal, and (3) bimodal. The extrapolation method is the default and preferred method since it uses the actual data supplied by user. The input data is extrapolated from zero volume to 100% of the spray volume since in many cases the smaller droplet size may not be measured. The normal and bimodal are provided as options to create a fit around the drop size distribution using a normal or bimodal probability distribution.

Droplet evaporation

Droplets generated by an agricultural spray nozzle are small, so they have enormous surface areas per unit volume of droplet and thus are subject to the effects of evaporation. The evaporation rate of water from the droplet is dictated by the rate at which heat is transferred from the surrounding air to the droplet. The primary driving force for this evaporation is the wet bulb temperature depression (DT_{wb}), i.e. the difference between the ambient air temperature and that at the surface of the droplet. The turbulence around the droplet, which is a function of the Reynolds number, changes the evaporation rate to a secondary extent due to changes in heat and mass transfer coefficient.

As droplets leave the spray nozzle, they cool down to the wet bulb temperature (from the tank solution temperature) by evaporative cooling until they reach a steady state wet bulb temperature. Then they continue reducing in size based on this wet bulb temperature depression driving force. This evaporation (and droplet diameter reduction) will continue until the droplet contains only the non-volatile formulation and active components as a solid or it deposits on a surface. The size reduction causes its terminal velocity to reduce so the horizontal wind carries the smaller droplets further before deposition. The model uses Equation 1 to track the mass of the droplet (m_w) by time (t):

$$dm_w(t)/dt = -\pi/4 * \lambda_w * \Delta T_{wb} * \rho_{Soln}(t) * D(t) * \left\{ 1 + 0.276 * Re_d^{0.5} \right\} * \left\{ \frac{m_w(t)/MW_{H_2O}}{[m_w(t)/MW_{H_2O} + m_s/MW_s]} \right\} \quad (\text{Eqn 1})$$

In Equation 1, which is derived from Holterman (2003), $D(t)$ is the droplet diameter, microns, DT_{wb} wet bulb depression temperature, °C, λ_w is evaporation rate constant set to 76.80 mm²/s-°C, ρ_{Soln} is solution density (g/cm³), Re_d is the Reynolds number. m_s and m_w are mass of dissolved solids and water in the droplet (grams), respectively. MW_s and MW_{H_2O} are the molecular weight of solids and water in the droplet, respectively.

Horizontal wind profile

The average horizontal wind velocity (U_x) is a logarithmic function of height (z) from the ground up and is usually defined based on atmospheric measurements at two to five heights from the ground above the sprayed fields. The CDM model uses a method described by Raupach (1994) to determine the develop the horizontal wind velocity (U_x) v. elevation (Z) profile. Since $U_x(z)$ is a function of height and z is a function of time for the droplet, this mathematical relationship defines the wind velocity surrounding the droplet along its path influences its trajectory until it hits the ground. The model solves the system of equations under the assumptions that all droplets sprayed eventually reach the ground. In practice, however, droplets deposit on leaves as well (primary intent), so from a drift standpoint, the model solution strategy is a worse case situation.

The average magnitude of the horizontal wind velocity over a crop canopy has a logarithmic profile vs elevation, reducing in magnitude with elevation reduction. As the elevation gets closer to the top of the crop canopy, this profile changes in shape to one more strongly influenced by the friction through the canopy. The profile shape is taken from Cionco (1965) dealing with a mature corn canopy.

Horizontal wind velocity is converted to a differential form for improved accuracy using Equation 2:

$$dU_x/dZ = U_f / \{0.40 * (Z(t) - d)\}, \text{ for } Z(t) \geq z_1 \text{ (Eqn. 2)}$$

where:

$$dU_x/dZ = (U_h/\kappa) * \exp(a_{avg} * [Z(t)/h_c - 1]) * \{1 + \alpha_{avg}/h_c * (Z(t) - z_0)\}, \text{ for } Z(t) < z_1$$

and where, κ within canopy wind velocity parameter, a_{avg} is canopy flow index, U_f is the velocity parameter for log-based equation above the canopy, U_h is the velocity parameter for equation form thru the canopy, z_1 elevation at which transition in profile occurs, h_c is the canopy height, d is the zero plane displacement, and z_0 is the friction length. In the above equation, z_1 is the elevation at which both the wind speed, and the derivative with respect to elevation are equal. If there is no canopy, then only the first equation is used. With or without a canopy, the integration is stopped when the elevation of the droplet (i.e. $Z(t)$) reaches a value just above z_0 .

Droplet transport

The CDM uses the work of Ragendran (2012) to predict the physical effect of breakup of droplets from the liquid sheet who showed that for any spray nozzle type, as pressure is increased (and liquid flow rate increases by the square root of the pressure), its emanating liquid velocity naturally increases.

The differential equations for droplet transport in two dimensions (x for horizontal distance from the centerline of the nozzle, z for elevation from ground) are solved in time for a geometric progression of droplet sizes spanning the droplet size distribution produced by the nozzle. Integration stops for every initial droplet size when each droplet hits the ground. Each differential equation system tracks distance and velocity of the droplet over time, and the droplet change in size due to water evaporation.

The initial droplet speed post disengagement from the liquid sheet is assumed to be the same speed as the spray from which they disengaged. This speed is computed using Bernoulli's equation, using the nozzle pressure and the liquid solution density.

The following time-based differential equation system is derived from the definition that the sum of the forces acting on a droplet moving through the atmosphere equals the time rate of change of momentum of that droplet. The final differential equation set represents the Lagrangian transport of water droplets through air in time. The integration of this system of equations provides the droplet horizontal and vertical velocities and the position of the droplet (relative to its starting point) over time.

$$\begin{aligned} d(m_d(t) * V_x(t))/dt &= \Sigma \text{ Forces in horizontal orientation} \\ d(m_d(t) * V_z(t))/dt &= \Sigma \text{ Forces in vertical orientation} \end{aligned}$$

Drag forces are defined as:

$$|F_{drag}| = Cd(Re_d) * A_s / 2 * |DV(t)|^2 = Cd(Re_d) * \pi / 4 * D(t)^2 * \{[U_x(z) - V_x(t)]^2 + [U_z(z) - V_z(t)]^2\}$$

where Cd is the drag coefficient (see Bilanin *et al*, 1989), A_s is projection area of the droplet, $|DV(t)|$ is the magnitude of droplet drag velocity. U_x and U_z are horizontal and vertical wind velocity in cm/sec.

$$\begin{aligned} F_{drag,x} &= |F_{drag}| * \cos(\theta) \\ F_{drag,z} &= |F_{drag}| * \sin(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

where θ is the angle made between drag force in x orientation and $|F_{drag}|$

$$\begin{aligned} \cos(\theta) &= [U_x(z) - V_x(t)] / \{[U_x(z) - V_x(t)]^2 + [U_z(z) - V_z(t)]^2\}^{0.5} \\ \sin(\theta) &= [U_z(z) - V_z(t)] / \{[U_x(z) - V_x(t)]^2 + [U_z(z) - V_z(t)]^2\}^{0.5} \end{aligned}$$

Σ Forces in vertical orientation:

$$d(m_d(t)*V_z(t))/dt = g_c * \rho_{Air} * \pi/6 * D(t)^3 - g_c * \rho_{Liq} * \pi/6 * D(t)^3 + Cd(Re_d) * \pi/4 * D(t)^2 * |DV(t)| * (U_z(z) - V_z(t))$$

Σ Forces in horizontal orientation = $F_{drag,x}$

$$d(m_d(t)*V_x(t))/dt = Cd(Re_d) * \pi/4 * D(t)^2 * |DV(t)| * (U_x(z) - V_x(t))$$

Droplet acceleration in the vertical (z) and horizontal direction (x) are calculated as follows:

$$dV_z(t)/dt = g_c * (\rho_{Air}/\rho_{Liq} - 1) + 3/4 * \rho_{Air}/\rho_{Liq} * \{Cd(Re_d)/D(t)\} * [U_z(z) - V_z(t)] * \{[U_x(z) - V_x(t)]^2 + [U_z(z) - V_z(t)]^2\}^{0.5} \text{ (Eqn. 3)}$$

$$dV_x(t)/dt = 3/4 * \rho_{Air}/\rho_{Liq} * \{Cd(Re_d)/D(t)\} * [U_x(z) - V_x(t)] * \{[U_x(z) - V_x(t)]^2 + [U_z(z) - V_z(t)]^2\}^{0.5} \text{ (Eqn. 4)}$$

$$dX(t)/dt = V_x(t) \text{ (Eqn. 5)}$$

$$dZ(t)/dt = V_z(t) \text{ (Eqn. 6)}$$

The droplet evaporation (Equation 1), horizontal wind profile (Equation 2), droplet acceleration (Equations 3 and 4), and droplet location (Equations 5 and 6) equations are solved simultaneously for each droplet size to arrive at the drift distance for each droplet size. These calculations are done for three initial vector velocities of the droplet, spanning the nozzle spray shape. It is assumed that each streamline of spray has the same droplet size distribution as provided by the nozzle data. This produces three vectors of downwind distance traveled to deposition vs initial droplet size.

Sprayed field and downwind deposition

The deposition part of the calculation breaks up the sprayed field into horizontal segments (perpendicular to the mean wind direction) and starting at the first segment (furthest from the downwind edge of the sprayed field) calculates how much of the sprayed volume by all the nozzles over that segment of a boom fall within that segment (Fig. 2). “The deposition calculations currently ignores the presence of the crop canopy relative to its impact on filtering spray droplets and preventing them from moving further downwind. The impact of the crop on wind velocity profile is included in the calculations. The lack of spray filtering from downwind canopy is ignored is for prediction of a conservative deposition profile. Future work will involve providing advanced options for spray filtering downwind crop. The horizontal position of the droplet is determined relative to its initial droplet size. This is done for the second segment and second nozzle on the boom and includes how much of the volume sprayed from the first nozzle/segment fall into the second segment.

Fig. 2. CDM deposition for sprayed area segments. Green curves are largest droplets (>350 microns), black dashed curves are medium droplets (150 to 350 microns), and red curves are smallest droplets (<150 microns).

The above is repeated for every segment until reaching the end of the field. The deposited volume per segment is stored in a matrix called deposited volume matrix (DVM) with rows representing the initial droplet size for each nozzle and columns representing the segments.

The same algorithm is used to account for deposition beyond the downwind edge of the field (drift field) but unlike in the sprayed field where the segment width is represented by the distance between nozzles, the width of the segments is chosen by another algorithm which is user-changeable.

The current model sets the number of segments in the drift part of the field equal to those in the sprayed field and a user can specify the drift distance of interest before the deposition calculations are done. The conversion of deposited volumes in each segment to concentrations (as percent of intended application rate) is done by using a turbulence model that disperses the deposited volumes statistically based on variations in horizontal wind direction with turbulence (Fig. 3). The variation in horizontal wind direction ($\Psi\Psi\Psi$) is equal to one sigma variation in wind direction (degrees) around the average wind speed during the spray application.

Fig. 3. Schematic of sprayed and drift segments simulated in the CDM. Turbulence ($\Psi\Psi\Psi$), which is based on variation in wind direction, is used to disperse the spray on drift segments.

Model Validation

The initial test of the model was a comparison against the Spray Drift Task Force (Johnson, 2021) dataset (Figs 4a and 4b). Three different nozzles were tested for drift with several tank mixes that varied in active conc and other adjuvants/surfactants. As can be seen in the plots below, the predicted deposition profile at drift distance (as % of applied application rate) is compared (y axis) against the data (x axis). Excellent comparison was achieved against each nozzle for randomly selected cases per nozzle.

Fig. 4a. Comparison of CDM output against SDTF datasets for various nozzles: (A) Nozzle 8004.

Fig. 4b. Comparison of CDM output against SDTF datasets for various nozzles (B) nozzle 8004 LP.

More recently, a comparison has been made against a subset of the SETAC DRAW database and similar results were achieved. Results are shown in Figs 5a and 5b.

Fig. 5a. Comparison of CDM output against selected SETAC DRAW datasets for various conditions: boom height (top right) and wet bulb depression (WBD) as a surrogate for evaporation (bottom left).

Discussion

The Casanova Drift Model is a mechanistic spray drift model for ground boom application. This model predicts droplet trajectory in two dimensions (height above ground, horizontal distance from nozzle centerline) over time until deposition. The droplet trajectory calculations simultaneously

Fig. 5b. Comparison of CDM output against selected SETAC DRAW datasets for various conditions: wind speed and country (top left); spray pressure as a surrogate for drop spectra (top right); and forward speed (bottom right); and wind speed and WBD combined (bottom left).

account for particle deceleration (in the vertical direction) towards its terminal velocity, deceleration and/or acceleration towards the horizontal wind velocity, and particle size and density changes due to water evaporation. The effect of wind velocity profile *vs* height is also taken into account, including the transition in profile shape from above to within the canopy. Model calculations are divided into two distinct phases. The phase I calculations provide a travel distance *v.* particle size function used for subsequent calculations. For phase II, the drop size distribution parameters used to generate the applied solution volume from each nozzle for each particle size over the sprayed field, then the travel distance *vs* particle size function is used to determine the sprayed volume depositing over the intended and drift field length. A comparison of predicted drift concentration profiles against data shows model describes the actual behaviour of the drift well.

In our initial assessment of the model's capabilities, the initial check against the SDTF data set was very encouraging (Fig. 4). However, when using the range of EU data (courtesy of the Belgian, Dutch, German, and French drift researchers who have contributed to the SETAC DRAW initiative [Mackay *et al.*, 2018]), we were aware that similar results would be unlikely. We were therefore most interested in seeing if the model would give equivalent relative results when compared with the original field trial data. In all cases, the CDM over-predicts deposition drift (although this is not necessarily a bad thing from a regulatory viewpoint). Boom height differences (50 cm *vs* 70 cm: (Fig. 5a top right) were relatively small in both data and model output. However, the CDM is overestimating by a factor of about five. The BE data selected for assessing evaporation (Fig. 5a bottom left) has a very good fit and the relative differences in evaporation are quite close which suggests that the CDM evaporation calculation is robust. However, the combination of WBD and wind speed (Fig. 5b bottom left) was less satisfactory: the model underestimates at low and overestimates at high windspeeds. Taking windspeed alone from NL and DE data (Fig. 5b top left),

it is clear “country” is a parameter that needs to be considered (here “country” covers different general climatic conditions and wind structure as well as different samplers and conditions of the trial). This data set clearly shows that the CDM is parameterised more towards explaining the NL data rather than the DE data. The last two comparisons – pressure (as a surrogate for drop size) and forward speed (Fig. 5b top right and bottom right, respectively) – shows that there is still work to be done on the model’s internal workings.

In general, all models are worked up from data sets. Thus, there is an inherent assumption that, for example, the samplers are collecting the real drift or that the method of obtaining droplet spectra supplies the true droplet spectra. This is not the case: different samplers have different capture efficiencies at different distances; different methods of drop size measurement can give quite different results. The CDM was initially calibrated against US data and the drop size protocol typically used in the US (spatial sampling with a Malvern instrument of the spray cloud accelerated to a common velocity). From the SETAC DRAW exercise, it is very clear that the EU data not only comes from very different climate (even within the EU) but represents quite different measurement protocols (e.g. samplers). This is the next important step to resolve in the model development.

Conclusions

The Casanova drift model is a useful tool in predicting drift from boom-based application of herbicides. It has been converted to a solution platform that makes run time a non-issue. In comparing the prediction of deposition to data, the model is very accurate near the edge of the field, whereas further downfield it tends to be conservative. The ultimate intent is to present this model to the regulatory agencies as a tool for their use, with more realistic buffer zones being extracted from these predictions.

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